

A LITERATURE REVIEW ON ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING

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Abstract: Approximately 10%–30% of women aged over 35 years experience abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB), one of the most frequent disorders observed in routine obstetrics and gynecology clinical practice.^{1,2} Excessive menstruation, intermenstrual bleeding, and ovulation issues are all collectively referred to as AUB.¹ More than half of AUB patients do not seek medical care; furthermore, AUB results in a lower quality of life and productivity and a poorer perinatal outcome for women with a history of anemia caused by AUB.³ Recently, many publications based on AUB have been added to the literature.

Keywords: abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB), fibroids, FIGO PALM-COEIN classification of AUB, polyps, menstruation, infertility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB), also known as hypermenorrhea, is defined by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists as bleeding that lasts longer than 7 days or results in a blood loss of more than 80 mL per menstrual cycle.⁴ However, it is challenging to precisely estimate the amount of menstrual blood in routine clinical practice. HMB is defined more broadly by the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) as excessive menstrual blood loss that impairs a woman's physical, emotional, social, and material wellbeing.⁵ Iron deficiency anemia frequently occurs as a result of AUB and uterine leiomyomas, endocrine abnormalities, and medical diseases like blood coagulation problems, which are some of the causes.

II. FIGO classification of cause: 'PALM-COEIN'

Once bleeding is defined as being abnormal, the acronym PALM-COEIN is now being increasingly used for categorizing causes: **P**olyp, **A**denomyosis,

Leiomyoma, **M**alignancy (and hyperplasia), **C**oagulopathy, **O**vulatory disorders, **E**ndometrial, **I**atrogenic and **N**ot otherwise classified [13]. The 'PALM' are assessed visually (imaging and histopathology) and the 'COEIN' are non-structural

Polyps (AUB-P)

Endometrial polyps are epithelial proliferations arising from the endometrial stroma and glands. The majority are asymptomatic. The contribution of polyps to AUB varies widely ranging from 3.7% to 65% [22], [23], but it is widely accepted [24]. The incidence of polyps as with fibroids increases with age and both pathologies may frequently co-exist, or suspected polyps visualised on transvaginal ultrasound scanning (TV-USS) may be mistaken for SM fibroids and vice-versa [25].

Adenomyosis (AUB-A)

The relationship between adenomyosis and AUB remains unclear [26], particularly with regard to wide variations in histopathological diagnosis reflecting variations in criteria used and also improved radiological diagnosis. Typically, adenomyosis is associated with increasing age and may co-exist with fibroids.

Malignancy (AUB-M)

Endometrial cancer is the most common gynaecological malignancy in the western world. With the reclassification by the WHO from hyperplasia to endometrial intraepithelial neoplasia (EIN), the current prevalence of premalignant disease is unknown. The evaluation of the endometrium may be affected by distortion of the uterine cavity by fibroids, and as such, the co-existing pathology may delay diagnosis. The diagnosis of cervical cancer should be considered, particularly with persistent intermenstrual bleeding, and rarely ovarian cancer may present with AUB.

Coagulopathy (AUB-C)

Coagulopathies are reported to affect 13% [40] of the women presenting with HMB. The majority of these women suffer from Von Willebrand disease [40]. Systemic disorders of haemostasis may be identified in 90% of women using a structured history

Anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy hitherto has been considered as a part of 'AUB-C' (rather than AUB-I).

Ovulatory (AUB-O)

Anovulatory cycles may contribute to AUB by unopposed oestrogen effects on the endometrium causing marked proliferation and thickening resulting in HMB along with an altered frequency of menstruation. This is observed at the extremes of reproductive age; however, impact on the HPO axis along with endocrinopathies is also present. The latter include polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), hyperprolactinaemia, hypothyroidism as well as factors such as obesity, anorexia, weight loss, mental stress and extreme exercise. Typically, women in this group have menstrual cycles that fall out with 38 days or have a variation of >21 days. Drugs that affect dopamine levels, with their attendant effects on the HPO axis, also currently fall under this category rather than AUB-I. In women with fibroids, the co-existing ovulatory dysfunction may exacerbate menstrual loss.

The FIGO AUB classification system is a dynamic system with feedback and contemporary debate informing future revisions [13]. The position of drug therapies affecting AUB is currently under review with regard to whether anticoagulant/antiplatelet therapies and drugs affecting the HPO axis may be better placed in 'AUB-I'.

Endometrial (AUB-E)

AUB that occurs in the context of a structurally normal uterus with regular menstrual cycles without evidence of coagulopathy is likely to have an underlying endometrial cause. Endometrial function in the context of menstruation and its disorders is still not fully understood and remains an area of active scientific enquiry, particularly the complexities of the sequence of events triggered

by progesterone withdrawal (due to demise of the corpus luteum in the absence of pregnancy). Hypoxia, inflammation, haemostasis and angiogenesis all play crucial roles in the shedding and subsequent scarless repair of the functional upper layer of the endometrium.

Iatrogenic (AUB-I)

Iatrogenic causes of AUB include exogenous therapy that may lead to unscheduled endometrial bleeding. This is typically due to the continuous oestrogen or progestin therapy (systemic or intrauterine delivery routes) or those interventions that act on ovarian steroid release such as gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) agonists and aromatase inhibitors. Selective oestrogen receptor modulators (SERMs) and more rarely selective progesterone receptor modulators (SPRMs) may cause AUB through direct action on the endometrium.

The use of an intrauterine device (IUD) may cause a low-grade endometritis which may also contribute to AUB.

Not otherwise classified (AUB-N)

It is inevitable that there will be pathologies that are either rare or poorly defined that do not easily fit within the categories described earlier. Examples include arteriovenous malformations, endometrial pseudoaneurysms, myometrial hypertrophy and chronic endometritis (not precipitated by an IUD).

III. Approach to management

Management of AUB-L should address fertility desire, impact of pressure symptoms, co-morbidities, and any other AUB contributors. Treatment should be individualised. In those with other underlying AUB causes co-existing with fibroids, targeted treatment of these may ameliorate bleeding, and in the absence of pressure symptoms or sub-mucosal myoma-related infertility, all the treatments may be required.

IV. Specific treatment options for individual PALM-COEIN causes of AUB.

AUB Sub-classification	Specific treatment
Polyp	Resection
Adenomyosis	Surgery: hysterectomy; adenomyomectomy (not frequently performed)
Malignancy	Surgery +/- adjuvant treatment High-dose progestogens (if surgery not possible) Palliation (including radiotherapy)
Coagulopathy	Tranexamic acid DDVAP
Ovulation	Lifestyle modification Cabergoline (if hyperprolactinaemia) Levothyroxine (if hypothyroid)
Endometrial	Specific therapies await further delineation of underlying mechanisms
Iatrogenic	Refer to FSRH CEU guidance on problematic bleeding with hormonal contraception [56]
Not otherwise classified	Antibiotics for endometritis Embolisation of AV malformation

V. Conclusions

AUB is a common and debilitating condition with high direct and indirect costs.

A structured approach to establishing the cause using the FIGO PALM-COEIN

classification system will facilitate accurate diagnosis and inform treatment options. The increased availability of medical options has expanded the choice for women. Many will no longer need to recourse to potentially complicated surgery. Treatment must remain individualised and encompass the impact of pressure symptoms, desire for retention of fertility and contraceptive needs, as well as address the management of their AUB in order to achieve improved quality of life.

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